
Introduction

In textile industries, chemical processing requires to the colouration of the textile substrate includes 4- processing steps being known as pre-treatments, dyeing or printing, finishing (Yang *et al.*, 2018). The textile industry recognizes the high pollution industry. Every step of chemical processing produces a huge amount of wastewater. The wastewater from printing and dyeing is distinguished by ordinary bio-degradability, high PH, intricate compositions, high chrominance, high turbidity and is emitted in large volume (Xu *et al.*, 2018). The treatment process of such effluent includes physical, chemical and biological technologies. Considering the high removal efficiency, the common treatment method includes physical adsorption and chemical oxidation etc. These treatment processes are expensive, energy-intensive, besides that needs some more steps to prepare the absorbent and decomposes by-product (Yang *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, the biological process consumes lower cost, lower energy consumptions and lofty efficiency are thought an undertaking selection for ample industrial applications. The biological sludge treatment mainly divided into two processes being known as an aerobic and anaerobic process. In aerobic activated sludge process air is circulated for the decompositions of the sludge. Whereas in anaerobic activated sludge treatment, the process is carried out by microorganisms. In anaerobic sludge treatments, as the name implies for the metabolism of these organisms do not use free oxygen. Despite the anaerobic process is slower than the aerobic process, some anaerobic process feature with limited energy consumptions, excellent efficiency, biogas productivity alongside improved stability (Xu *et al.*, 2018). Many types of research have been published for the development of the anaerobic process. In the interest of content, here the recent process of an anaerobic textile effluent treatment system i.e. expanded granular sludge bed has summarized with details.

The concepts of Expanded Granular Sludge Bed or Blanket Bioreactor

Expanded granular sludge bed (EGSB) is considered as third generations anaerobic bioreactor based on the Up-flow anaerobic sludge Blanket i.e. UASB (Xu *et al.*, 2018). The basic concepts of EGSB include the circulations of air by an external system which initiates the mass transports performance and the connection between the effluent and microorganism (Xu *et al.*, 2018). The main operating conditions of EGSB bioreactor comprises on the rate of organic loading (OLR), diameter to height ratio, Temperature, hydraulic-retention-time (HRT), P^H , up-flow velocity (V_{up}), bed expansion, and the types of effluent. These effective variables initiate its performance and efficiency which involve in organic substrate removal efficiency and biogas productions (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). Usually, if the effluent contains toxic materials then the activity and metabolism of these microorganisms supposed to be inhibited (Xu *et al.*, 2018).

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of EGSB bio-reactor.

Formation of the EGSB Bioreactor

The EGSB bioreactor consists of GLS 3-phase separator zone or settling zone, transition zone and digester zone. The sludge bed height must be up to 55-65% of the actual height of the bioreactor. The settling zone is located in the upper portion of the bioreactor having a radius up to six times bigger than in the digester zone (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). The settling zone permits to separate the treated effluent from anaerobic granular sludge (AGS) and air. The digester zone is the area where the pollutant of the wastewater undergoes chemical transformation (remove up to 85-95% of the pollutants remains in the liquid-state) with the help of microbial digestion present in the AGS. The property which puts the EGSB bioreactors more promising in the field of effluent treatment is the recirculations of the medium which permits assistance in diluting biodegradable restrictive and toxic materials, initially present in the effluent. Due to recirculation, the EGSB bioreactor can perform under adverse conditions i.e. toxic substrate or restrictive substrate

including effluent generated by the Textile, pharmaceutical and chemical industry (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

Figure 2: The Schematic diagram of an EGSB bioreactor. (1) Feed Reservoir, (2) Peristaltic Pump, (3) Water distributor, (4) Sludge bed zone, (5) Recirculation zone, (6) Bell Separation, (7) Biogas Outlet, (8) Gas flowmeter, (9) Effluent, (10) 3-phase separator zone or settling zone, (11) Transition Zone, (12) Digestion zone. (egsb.png, 2018)

Working principles of EGSB bioreactor

The working principles of an EGSB bioreactor relate to the recirculation of effluents as a function of the sludge treatment process. The recirculation process dilutes the toxic material in the effluent hence improves mass transfer and initiate biodegradation (Xu *et al.*, 2018). The sludge treatment process required after wastewater treatment process including preliminary, secondary, tertiary and some additive treatments i.e., filtration, decolourisation and disinfection. The EGSB bioreactor has a higher up-flow velocity ratio or height/diameter ratio remains 10:1 up to 25:1. Due to higher up-flow velocity ration (V_{up}) the reaching value for the liquid and gas respectively remains 6 m/h to even higher 20 m/h and 7 m/h (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). Generally, the waste is accumulated in a feed reservoir connecting with a peristaltic pump and a water distributor. The water distributor has a higher reaching value and puts the waste in a sludge bed zone where the microorganism is initially added for the treatment purposes being known as AGS. The significance of the higher velocity ratio provides greater contact between the wastewater and AGS allowing a high OLR rate up to 35-45 kg COD/m³d and the HTR for low strength wastewater and high strength wastewater remains respectively (0.2-2)

days and up to 15 days. (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). For low strength, wastewater recirculation is not required. The recirculation zone allows to diluting the toxic substance and biodegradable inhabitants which initiate efficient internal mixing of AGS and wastewater. After the recirculation process, the AGS and wastewater substrate goes for further processing zone including the settling zone, transition zone and digestion zone (Figure: 2). The 3-phase separator zone do the alternative process of recirculation process allowing the separation of AGS and wastewater substrate (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). In the transition zone, the substrate is preserved for the interest of biodegradation and the size distribution. Due to stratifications and size distributions the rate of biodegradation, compositions of AGS, the specific activity of AGS changes at the pick of the digestion zone. In anaerobic EGSB bioreactor, the activity of neurotrophic activity decreases from the bottom to the top of the digestion zone allowing the methanogenic activity as a source of biogas (CH_4) production. In digestion zone the activity of microorganisms and P^H levels are maintain by some chemical treatment. Finally, the sludge is ready to decompose in the soil without doing any harm of the environment (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

Factor Influencing the performance of EGSB bioreactor

The characteristics of wastewater: The characteristics of the wastewater depends on its biodegradability index. Biodegradability index is a ratio of BOD and COD (biochemical oxygen demand). The recommended BOD/COD ratio must be greater than 0.3 which indicates that if 30% of the organic substance present in the wastewater it will be biodegradable. Whereas if the biodegradability ration is lower than 0.3, the wastewater cannot be treated by EGSB reactor because the performance would be very low (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

The potential of Hydrogen (P^H): The potential of hydrogen

affects the process of the bioreactor allowing a good digestive improvement of the microorganism and the substrate directly. Normally, the suitable P^H range for the EGSB bioreactor remains 6.5-7.5 which initiate the digestion process of the microorganism (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

Temperature (T): The anaerobic can be run under three temperature levels with an optimal temperature range 20 °C being known as psychrophilic level, the other two range respectively 25-40 °C and 40°C being known as mesophilic and thermophilic levels (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

Retention Time (RT): RT has considered the average time of a particle remains in a certain volume in a continuous process. It is initiated with a growth rate of microbial means (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019). Two types of RT are evaluated: HRT (residence time of waste in the reactor) & SRT (average time of the microorganism in solid-state).

Figure 3: Factors influencing the performance of EGSB bioreactor.

Hydraulic retention time (HRT): HRT (h or d) refers to the ratio of the volume (v) of the bioreactor (m^3) to the influent flow rate (m^3/d), denoted by Q . HRT can be calculated by using Eq. 1 (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

$$HRT = \frac{v}{Q} \quad 1$$

Where v = volume of the bioreactor (m^3) and Q = influent flow rate (m^3/d).

Up-flow velocity (V_{up}): Up-flow velocity ratio refers to a limiting factor as to treat effluent with a high concentration of microorganism as well as suspended solids. By increasing the V_{up} ratio it may increase the HSR, which obviates the removal of obsessive sedimentation velocity of microbial matter and consequently degrade the performance of bioreactor (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).

Application area

The EGSB bioreactor is applicable regarding the treatment process of enormous toxic substance producing industries including Textile, chemical, pharmaceutical and agro-industrial as well as domestic (Yang *et al.*, 2018).

Advantage of EGSB bioreactor

- ✚ The EGSB bioreactor generates low pathogen (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ High OLR (Organic loading rate), fair stock resistance comparing to the UASB and ABR bioreactor systems (Xu *et al.*, 2018).
- ✚ Process control is easy and the backwashing process is not required.
- ✚ The methanogenic activity produces biogas which is considered one of the major advantage of EGSB bioreactor (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ The EGSB bioreactor can use under adverse conditions including toxic substance (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ The construction of EGSB bioreactor is simple and convenient as it takes a small land for the setup purposes (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ The recirculation process of EGSB initiates a better interaction between the AGS and the toxic substance (Xu *et al.*, 2018).

The disadvantage of EGSB bioreactor

- ✚ During the anaerobic possible odours are generated due to the presence of H_2S (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ Long startup times due to the chemical. Biological and physical parameters i.e., concentration and compositions of effluent (Cruz-Salomón *et al.*, 2019).
- ✚ The retention of biomass can face some problems due to the nature of wastewater.

Conclusions

Various types of wastewaters which come from numerous industries including Textile, chemical, pharmaceutical, agro-industrial as well as from the domestic. This wastewater or effluent contains hazardous toxic substance allowing pollutions on the different segment of the environment. The anaerobic EGSB bed bioreactor can be feasible to dilute inhibitory from the wastewater following biodegradation. The EGSB bioreactor can be a sustainable substitute for the effective treatment of numerous types of pollutants remains in wastewater as compared to other treatment processes. The EGSB bioreactor can be used under adverse conditions i.e. toxic substance. The EGSB bioreactor produces low pathogens which are taken in the sludge bed and also to the nutrient's removal. In conclusion, it can be said EGSB bioreactor offering a good effluent treatment process besides biogas production. That is why it is considered as the most promising treatment process of wastewater (Xu *et al.*, 2018).

Abbreviations

EGSB: Expanded Granular Sludge Bed or Blanket; **UASB:** Up-flow anaerobic Sludge Bed or Blanket; **AGS:** Anaerobic Granular Sludge; **GLS:** Gas liquid-solid; **OLR:** Organic loading rate; **HRT:** Hydraulic retention time; **COD:** chemical oxygen demand; **BOD:** Biological oxygen demand; **HSR:** Hydraulic shear rate.

References

- Cruz-Salomón, A. *et al.* (2019) 'Expanded granular sludge bed bioreactor in wastewater treatment', *Global Journal of Environmental Science and Management*, 5(1), pp. 119–138. doi: 10.22034/gjesm.2019.01.10.
- egsb.png(651×1024)* (2018). Available at: <http://photos1.blogger.com/blogger/2/4279/2760/1600/egsb.png> (Accessed: 10 February 2021).
- Xu, H. *et al.* (2018) 'Recent advances in anaerobic biological processes for textile printing and dyeing wastewater treatment: a mini-review', *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 34(11), pp. 1–9. doi: 10.1007/s11274-018-2548-y.
- Yang, B. *et al.* (2018) 'Performance evaluation of anaerobic baffled reactor (ABR) for treating alkali-decrement wastewater of polyester fabrics at incremental organic loading rates', *Water Science and Technology*, 77(10), pp. 2445–2453. doi: 10.2166/wst.2018.194.

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